

A Descriptive Analysis of Social Entrepreneurship

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ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurs are creative problem solvers who are highly driven and able to think critically; these traits are paired with a desire to address social issues, a social entrepreneur emerges. A person who has an inventive solution to one of society's most critical and challenging social issues is referred to be a social entrepreneur. They are relentless and ambitious, tackling pressing societal concerns and putting up fresh suggestions for significant changes in society. India desperately needs this new generation of sociopreneurs to develop novel business concepts. Therefore, in order to bring about the necessary social changes, social entrepreneurship identifies a social issue and applies entrepreneurial concepts to plan, launch, and manage a social business. The most successful forms of social entrepreneurship lead to incremental improvements in the near term. This study discusses the role of social entrepreneurs. Further, it identifies several obstacles faced by social entrepreneurs and makes an effort to provide some solutions to these issues.

Keywords: Social entrepreneur, Role, SWOC analysis, Business entrepreneur.

1. INTRODUCTION :

One of the concepts most often misinterpreted in the nonprofit sector in the modern era is "social entrepreneurship." Between 1960 and 1970, the literature on social transformation was where the terms "social entrepreneur" and "social entrepreneurship" were first employed. Bill Drayton, the creator of Asoka, pushed the phrase between 1980 and 1990, when it first became widely used. Tony Blair, the Prime Minister of the United Kingdom, has lauded the rise of social entrepreneurs for their role in reshaping England's volunteer sector. Senior executives in the independent sector also spoke about the importance of social entrepreneurs. In India, a person is considered to be a social entrepreneur if they are either the founder, co-founder, or main functionary of a social entrepreneur organisation. The phrase "social entrepreneurship" takes into account the three methods of fusing business with social effect and creating for social consequences. In order to solve social issues creatively and to uphold social principles, one must engage in social entrepreneurship [1-3].

2. RELATED WORKS :

Systematic literature review on Social Entrepreneurship is given below.

Table 1: Related works on Social Entrepreneurship

S. No	Contribution	Reference
1.	The "Millennium Development Goals (MDG)" may provide a reliable operationalization of social demands in the developing world, according to the study paper "Social Entrepreneurship - A Way to Bring Social Change" The MDGs allude to the most important societal issues that must be addressed right now. The eradication of severe poverty and famine, obtaining universal access to "basic education, advancing gender equality and women's suffrage, lowering infant mortality, enhancing maternal health, and battling HIV/AIDS, malaria,	[4]

	and other illnesses” are just a few of the objectives listed. For instance, weaknesses in the social welfare system may provide opportunity for social entrepreneurs in industrialized nations. The opportunity landscape for social entrepreneurs has to be mapped, and it is also important to determine if and how the nature of social possibilities influences the entrepreneurial process.	
2	The government's role in the socioeconomic sphere is evolving toward the privatisation of public obligations in order to create value for society. As a direct consequence of this trend, charitable organisations are receiving a smaller share of public cash, while the popularity of social entrepreneurship is growing around the globe. The emphasis of social entrepreneurs is on “social services, employment & training, the environment (including cleantech and bio-systems), education, and community development”, according to research into the areas of operation of social businesses in Europe. Thus, the development in social companies might have a positive impact on public finances broadly. Additionally, the allure of social companies as potential places of employment is growing.	[5]
3	The Canadian Centre for Social Entrepreneurship published a paper titled "Young Social Entrepreneurs in Canada" that claims that social entrepreneurship is defined by a focus on “social innovation via entrepreneurial solutions. By emphasising hybrid forms of for-profit and nonprofit operations, socially entrepreneurial activities blur the conventional distinctions between the public, private, and nonprofit sectors”. In this model, cross-sectoral partnerships and the creation of radical new ways to addressing long-standing and complicated social and economic issues are both assumed to exist. The past ten years have seen a widespread acceptance of social entrepreneurship in both the United States and the United Kingdom. As a result, substantial institutional and organisational resources have appeared in each of these nations to promote and assist budding social entrepreneurs and their endeavours.	[6]
4	According to his study, "Social Entrepreneurship- A Growing Trend in the Indian Economy," social entrepreneurship is "the awareness of a social issue and the application of entrepreneurial concepts to the organisation, creation, and management of a social enterprise in order to bring about a desired social change." Whereas, a commercial entrepreneur often gauges success by profit and return, in contrast, a social entrepreneur also considers the benefits to society as a whole. Therefore, the primary objective of social entrepreneurship is to progressively expand the scope of objectives related to society, culture, and the environment. It is usual to identify social entrepreneurs with the volunteer and not-for-profit sectors; however, this does not mean that social entrepreneurs cannot make a profit. The activity of social entrepreneurship with a global perspective or within an international setting is referred to as "international social entrepreneurship." Muhammad Yunus, the creator and director of Grameen Bank and its expanding family of social enterprise companies, is a well-known contemporary social entrepreneur and in 2006, he was awarded the “Nobel Peace Prize.”	[7]
5	According to a new report titled "Social Entrepreneurship in India- Unveiling the Unlimited Opportunities" published by Swissnex India. 2015 highlights the fact that social entrepreneurship in terms of operation and leadership may be relevant to nonprofit organisations to the same extent as it may be applied to for-profit social enterprises, despite the fact that they are extremely different in terms of activities and legal structure. The social for-profit business, the non-profit model, and the hybrid model are the types of social entrepreneurship that may be found in India; the following sections go into more information about each of these models. In addition to the models listed above, corporate social responsibility	[8]

	(CSR) and philanthropy are further avenues for making a difference in India. The amount of money donated by charitable organisations all over the world to India continues to remain consistent. Recently, there has been an increase in the amount of donations made locally by affluent people who have both short-term and long-term vision. A new generation of high-net-worth people from the business sector are considering charitable initiatives in the form of investments and grants. The practise of strategic philanthropy in India is still in its infant stages at the moment.	
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3. OBJECTIVES :

- (1) To understand the concept of social entrepreneurship.
- (2) To explore the role of social entrepreneurs.
- (3) To analyze social entrepreneurship using SWOC analysis.

4. METHODOLOGY :

The study collects data through secondary sources by referring published scholarly articles, web pages and books from google scholar, research gate, SSRN and academia. Further, the study is analyzed using SWOC analysis.

5. SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA – AN OVERVIEW :

Prior to privatisation and international cooperation, there existed the recommended height of the Indian economy. Today, there is a new form of entrepreneurship that is emerging that aims to find a solution for other India, the one whose forgotten face hid in a tangle of development statistics. This new style of entrepreneurship is attempting to find a solution for India.

Table 2: Social entrepreneur in India

S. NO	Social Entrepreneur	Activities
(1)	Jeroo Billmoria	Is a successful businessperson who has founded a number of non-governmental organisations (NGOs) throughout the world. Her efforts have gained her recognition from organisations such as the Skill Foundation, the Ashoka Innovations for the Public, and the Schwab Foundation for Social Entrepreneurship.
(2)	Ajaita Shah	Working with SKS Microfinance and Ujjivan Financial Services for five years, she is ranked by Business Week as the most powerful leader under 30. She conceptualised the Frontier Markets Group. One of the requirements to become an Echoing Green Fellow is a commitment to helping 30 million rural families within three years.
(3)	Harish Hande	In Karnataka alone, the SELCO founder is credited for constructing 120,000 systems with the goal of making renewable energy the main source of electricity in rural India. Stressing as a keen observer of little things, he later developed into an inventor and a social entrepreneur.
(4)	Sushmita Ghosh	She focuses on repairing and reselling antiques and handmade items from rural India, which has helped make Rangasutra (a business) a success. These skilled and hardworking peasants provide her with what she refers to as "priceless" items, and she helps them earn the income they rightfully deserve.
(5)	Trilochan Shastry	In order to get politicians to admit to their wrongdoings, he filed a PIL, which subsequently resulted in a ruling. His efforts resulted in the formation of the ADR (Associations for Democratic Reform), which is in charge of vetting the elections every five years. Politicians are being held to a higher standard, which is raising public knowledge of what the Indian Constitution's Fundamental Rights really include.
(6)	Hanumappa	The recipient of the Indian Social Entrepreneur of the Year award for

	Sudarshan-	2014, which was presented by the Indian Minister of Finance Arun Jaitley. The Karuna Trust, a company involved in healthcare services, was founded by him. The prestigious Schwab Foundation for Social Entrepreneurship is the organisation behind this award.
(7)	Sanjit "Bunker" Roy	One of India's most lauded and well-known individuals to work in the field of social entrepreneurship. He started the Barefoot College and is an Indian social activist and educator. For his efforts to educate illiterate and semiliterate rural Indians, he was chosen as one of Time's 100 most important people in 2010. Originally known as Barefoot College, Bunker is credited with founding it. In 1972, Roy founded the Social Work and Research Centre after a review of water resources in 100 locations vulnerable to drought. Its goal quickly shifted from irrigation and water to empowerment and sustainability. The initiatives focused on offering training as paramedics for local medical care, installing water pumps near communities and teaching the local people how to maintain them without relying on outside mechanics, and using solar power to reduce reliance on kerosene lighting and the amount of time spent doing so. He received recognition in Time magazine in 2010 for the college's programmes, which have taught more than 3 million individuals in a variety of professions, including solar engineers, teachers, midwives, weavers, architects, and physicians.

6. ROLE OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURS :

Due to the low socioeconomic inequities present in developed cultures, there is little room for social entrepreneurship. However, socioeconomic disparities are greatest in developing, least developed, and undeveloped countries. Every entrepreneur has a heavy burden of duty, but social entrepreneurs have a particularly heavy burden since they are essential to the advancement of society. Selfless individuals who use entrepreneurial talents coupled with management skills for societal advantages and non-personal profits are the only ones who can create social value, social gains, and social reforms. These kind individuals are known as social entrepreneurs [9]. Given here, with regard to Indian society, are the tasks and responsibilities of social entrepreneurs.

- (1) Social entrepreneurs have the power to change society via the creation of distinctive goods or services that promote social advancement. Their job starts with determining the social issue, which affects the whole population of the society rather than a particular subgroup of individuals in that community. Therefore, it's crucial to choose the right social issue or concern.
- (2) Social entrepreneurs in India encounter various challenges associated with the mentality of individuals in their country who are resistant to changing the method in which they do business. The most important function of social entrepreneurs is to encourage people to bring about fundamental societal changes that will have a ripple effect across the whole society.
- (3) Social entrepreneurship relies on social innovations; the trick is to develop these innovations in a way that uses the least amount of resources possible to fully address the social issue.
- (4) Social entrepreneurs must reach the remotest corners of the nation to help underprivileged social groups. Social entrepreneurs have a duty to connect with these individuals and provide them with helpful services.
- (5) Social entrepreneurs are expected to create jobs as well with their own strategies. The most important task that social entrepreneurs have is to provide jobs for individuals in the community who meet certain requirements in terms of their level of education and experience.
- (6) Bringing about observable changes in communities via a social balancing strategy is one of the crucial tasks that social entrepreneurs must play in India's society.
- (7) Social entrepreneurs are tasked with eliminating inequality in society via the implementation of constructive solutions. Therefore, it is necessary to do thorough and sufficient research on the segment of the population into whom the product or service will be included.

7. SWOC ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP :

This framework helps in analyzing the strengths, weakness, opportunities and challenges of any business ideas and concepts [10]. The following are the SWOC analysis of social entrepreneurship:

Strengths:

- (1) It is very simple to market and promote these organisations. Since a social issue has a remedy, it is simpler to grab the public's and the media's attention. The level of attention a solution receives is often correlated with its degree of originality.
- (2) The socially conscious organisations will also get assistance from the government and society. Putting the business motivation second boosts an organization's standing in the public's eyes.
- (3) The idea of effecting positive social change is the driving force behind social companies, which in turn provide its founders with the personal gratification of having accomplished their goals.

Weakness:

- (1) Lack of better and more reactive equipment prevents social entrepreneurs from obtaining innovative technologies and a progressive perspective on business.
- (2) Competent labour from a variety of sources, including workers, professionals who volunteer, and members of the community, is needed for social entrepreneurship. The social entrepreneurs face significant hurdles in their efforts to inspire the participation of every member of this group in the organization's long-term development. Lack of trained labour is a problem for social business.
- (3) For Indian social entrepreneurs, a lack of funding is one of their biggest obstacles. As a result, they must either use their own money or borrow money from local lenders at exorbitant interest rates to operate their businesses. It puts a strain on their finances. These kinds of social entrepreneurs are not eligible for loans from banks.

Opportunities:

- (1) Government programmes and incentives for social entrepreneurs are extensive. Because of the ethical nature of the investing sector in this region, it is simpler to raise money at rates lower than the market average. Therefore, ethical entrepreneurs may get funding at lower costs. Social firms may also get grants, subsidies, and donations.
- (2) Given that the venture has a social component, it is simpler to win over supporters of similar minds. Hiring employees is simpler and the cost of doing so is cheaper than in most other fields.
- (3) The social argument that is supported makes it simpler for social companies to join foreign marketplaces. If recognised and praised, the societal transformation has the potential to provide numerous opportunities.

Challenges:

- (1) The government does not provide its stamp of approval to the vast majority of social businesses. The acknowledgment is necessary to support it by financial and legislative incentives, including the reform of tax legislation, the removal of onerous rules, the avoidance of arbitrary decision-making, and other demands that impede social entrepreneurs.
- (2) There are no financial advantages or subsidies offered for social entrepreneurships, and government laws and regulations are quite complicated and stringent. The government does not make these kinds of social businesses eligible for financial support or facilities in any way.
- (3) The biggest barrier to entrepreneurship in India is traditional schooling. The primary source of trained labour for entrepreneurship is the education sector. The conventional schooling system in India is unable to provide qualified human resources for social enterprise.
- (4) The perception of social workers who temporarily work for social entrepreneurs. Social workers, individuals who assist businesses, and non-governmental organisations (NGEO) do not make contributions as a form of financial support to social entrepreneurs.

- (5) Insufficient Future-Oriented Resources. There is no promotion of awareness since the breadth of social problems for the future is so narrow.

8. CONCLUSION :

Social entrepreneurs have a lot of potential. Businesspeople who focus on social issues are crucial to India's progress. They provide people access to a bright future for India, assist to reduce poverty, and inspire optimism. Due to a number of obstacles, such as a lack of government clearance and support, inadequate amounts of capital, and inadequate equipment, the conventional education system in India faces difficulties. The forward momentum of the social entrepreneurs' activity came to a halt. In order to accomplish the goal, a social entrepreneur has to be willing to embrace the advances in technology and make use of talented human resources. There is a duty on the part of the government to assist and offer social entrepreneurs with financial funding, as well as initiative facilities, technological equipment, and other resources as they work to discover issues and develop solutions related to social obligations.

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